

CLIMAREST

Deliverable 3.2

Report on the features of the experimental designs for marine restoration actions on demonstration sites and over

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Abstract

A literature review has been conducted to assess which experimental designs are adopted for restoration across marine ecosystems along the EU Seas and behind. Documents have been selected for showing the logic and the designs adopted in the most relevant studies showing restoration success. Overall ca 25 references are included in the document to support the description of experimental designs. The output of this literature review is included in the Deliverable 3.2: Report on the features of the experimental designs for marine restoration actions on demonstration sites and over.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

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Summary

Restoration is considered an effective strategy to accelerate the recovery of biological communities at a local scale. Recent initiatives in restoration demonstrated that it can be carried out also at large scale addressing the same scales of human pressures. Despite several success stories, the effects of restoration actions in the marine ecosystems are still unpredictable. Recent reviews highlighted the importance of several factors contributing to restoration effectiveness, able to decrease unpredictability of results (Fraschetti et al., 2021) such as site selection and restoration techniques. In addition, methodologies related to “protecting” the restored site, for example through the removal of invasive species or the use of protective mesh cages, have been found to have a significant positive influence on the outcomes of restoration. However, one issue that should be considered central in restoration, as in all ecological studies, is the importance of rigorous experimental designs to implement restoration interventions, assess restoration success and related drivers.

This deliverable has been conceived to show examples of experimental designs adopted to test the role of different interventions and processes (methodologies, substrates, adult presence, herbivory, gradients of pressures) across the habitats included in the project.

1. Experimental designs in ecological restoration

Restoration is a costly process (Bayraktarov et al., 2019). This often translates into the choice of limiting the efforts (e.g. replication in space and time) in the field and under laboratory conditions. This should never happen since it corresponds to serious consequences in terms of correct assessments of the effects of restoration interventions, success and failures, with the impossibility to provide the correct guidelines to practitioners. Measuring and explaining the variability inherent in ecological systems is not an easy task and systems needing ecological restoration are featured by the same large variability characterizing most natural systems.

International Standards of Ecological Restoration (Gann et al., 2019) recognize the need for carefully planning rigorous experimental designs to support robust restoration interventions. This issue has been recently covered also in specific meta-analyses (Tedford & Castorani, 2022) who showed that understanding the controls on variation in oyster predation strength, able to compromise restoration effectiveness, is impeded by inconsistencies in experimental methodologies.

To understand the outcomes of restoration, and to avoid spatial confounding, it is necessary to compare the putative impacted area with more than one reference area several times before and several times after the intervention, with the same number of replicates in each area and at each time. This approach has a long history and is an evolution of the Before-After-Control-Impact or BACI experimental designs. It is called beyond-BACI (Fig. 1) and increases the ability to unambiguously identify cause-effect relationships between anthropogenic disturbance and responses of natural populations (Underwood, 1993). Such formal monitoring has been largely used in environmental

impact assessments and in studies of the effectiveness of protection of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). The use of this logical framework can be also extended to active restoration. When studies of human interventions are carried out in single sites, the analysis becomes *asymmetrical* since there is only one single affected/protected/restored area to be compared with multiple control areas. The procedure is based on the comparison between the putatively impacted/protected/restored areas and multiple controls, sampled at different times before and after the intervention (Fig. 1). In most cases, however, no data are available before a disturbance occurred, before the establishment of an MPA, or before a restoration intervention is planned. In such a case, it is still possible to analyze the hypothesis that the protected/impacted/restored populations or assemblages differ from those in non-treated reference areas. Also in this case, analogously to what was described above for environmental impact assessment, multiple controls are needed to separate natural patterns of variability from the effects of the factor involved in the analyses (disturbance, protection, restoration). The classification of success, partial success, and failure is impracticable in case studies where the criteria to evaluate restoration success are not based on a formal comparison between restored sites (single or multiple) and replicated controls. This kind of experimental design increases the ability to unambiguously identify cause-effect relationships between specific interventions (e.g., anthropogenic disturbance, protection, other treatments) and responses of natural populations. Spatial confounding or pseudoreplication (Hurlbert, 1984) are a consequence of the absence of multiple ‘control’ areas in studies of human interventions. We also emphasize the need of repeating measurements in time, to estimate temporal variability of response variables.

Fig. 1. Beyond-BACI design for the assessment of environmental impact. The procedure is based on the comparison between putatively impacted areas (in this figure only one) and multiple controls sampled at different times before and after the intervention (indicated by the arrow). In case the intervention would be relative to restoration, we expect an increase in the selected response variable, compared to controls (see Underwood, 1993 for further details).

It is important to stress that controls must have the same type of habitat as the area selected for restoration and should be featured by the same ecological processes occurring in the restored area.

“Ideal” controls do not exist: they should always be randomly selected among those potentially representing the ecological processes of the same area where the intervention is occurring.

Here we provide a selection of experiments that have been conceived to test specific hypotheses in restoration intervention. We anticipate that in many cases it was difficult or even impossible to derive with precision how the study was carried out in the field, since most studies lack of relevant information on the logic and the design behind the experiment, and considering the factors included in the analyses. All cited literature comes from peer-reviewed journals. Thus, most of times, rather than specific criticism across the reported examples, final comments will stress common limits encountered in this Deliverable, introducing specific suggestions to increase the consistency of the results.

2. Case Studies in Climarest

The project has included five Case Studies conceived to improve the status of different ecosystems. Climarest has the final aim to provide guidelines to solve very common environmental issues adopting different approaches (from restoration to mitigation and monitoring). A description of the activities follows.

2.1 Svalbard, Norway

This Case Study develops in two habitats:

Shores: preventing further erosion in Arctic beaches with loose sediments.

Soft bottom: similar substrate to reference conditions within the end of the project.

Species target & habitat: no target species but target ecosystem types: 1) arctic littoral shores and 2) soft sediment bottom. The biodiversity target is to increase diversity of species.

Location: Adventfjorden (Svalbard)

Criteria for site selection: an urban site that is threatened by coastal erosion (primary site), a cultural heritage site that is threatened by coastal erosion (secondary site). Reference either to a rocky coastline or a stable (no coastal erosion) sedimentary coast.

Soft bottom: Sampling stations in a transect away from the sewage outlet and in a reference fjord. The reference needs to have similar features, but it should be without human impact.

Adopted experimental design: Experimental design for the assessment of outcomes: BACI (before/after/control/impact)

Description of the protocol and activity

Shores: flora and fauna biodiversity at the coastal and shore and shoreface. Video survey with blue eye for flora and fauna. Visual survey for fauna (birds) and onshore flora. Yearly frequency of surveys.

Soft bottom: Soft bottom fauna diversity characterization (3 grabs from tentatively 5 stations in a transect from the outlet and in the reference fjord), eDNA profiles of sediments and bottom water compared to diversity analysis. Pollution characterization; Sampling of sediments by grab, quantify

litter, sample for microplastics and chemical pollution (3 grabs from each station, tentatively 5 stations in the polluted fjord and one station in the reference). Waters samples at 3 depths of all stations for investigations of spreading of the plume. Sampling in the fjord once a year. Sampling of sewage with characteristics of pollution, nutrients and oxygen consumption during degradation before and after the sewage sieve monthly in collaboration with Longyearbyen lokalstyre. Samples of the waste material removed at the sewage sieve. Before and during social campaigns: Sample different branches of the sewage network to see if the campaigns have higher effects in some areas than others. Areas are largely separated into housing, hotels and restaurants, school and kindergarten, industrial area and the airport. Compare before and after levels of pollutants and waste.

2.2 Ireland

This Case Study focuses on seagrass restoration.

The restoration intervention is presently carried out in three locations with replicated donor meadows and receiving sites.

Fig. 2. Distribution of the experimental sites for the restoration of the seagrass meadows in Ireland.

At present, activities are focused on the collection of material for study population genetics of *Zostera* spp. across Ireland (4 out of 20 sites), site selection and characterization of environmental conditions to ensure favorable growth conditions for seagrass restoration. A small-scale seagrass restoration study and monitoring of indicators of transplantation success is on-going in 4 sites and the engagement of relevant stakeholders and formation of a citizen science network for future monitoring and assessment of restoration tools and strategies is on-going.

2.3 France

The restoration objectives within Climarest are to initiate restoration of native oyster reefs at the scale of 100 to 1000m² within the timeframe of the project

Species target & habitat: *Ostrea edulis* reefs

Location: Quiberon bay and bay of Brest

Criteria for site selection: Remaining wild populations

Adopted experimental design: Deployment of replicated reefs supporting settlement and growth of native oyster and catalyzing the formation of a three-dimensional biogenic reef. Phased deployment of reef structures between year 1 and year 2.

Year 1: demonstration and monitoring of upscaled reef implementation. All reefs are deployed in the same site, chosen for its good potential in terms of recruitment. The reefs will face different treatments, two of which at least will be predator removal vs. no predator removal.

Year 2: complementary deployment to evaluate conditions and processes for restoration in sites not prone to good recruitment.

Material: Artificial reefs used as early colonizing substrates.

2.4 Spain

The objective is to develop nature-based solutions to mitigate the impact of mussel farming on benthic ecosystems, secondary production and C, N and P fluxes to higher trophic levels. Expected outcomes are:

- Increase the resilience of communities and populations of interest below mussel farms.
- Develop restoration techniques for invertebrate and fish populations of commercial interest affected by overfishing and the effect of climate change.
- Restocking and stock enhancement of the population of European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) providing shelter and increasing food availability.
- Analyse the possibility of developing IMTA to promote the use of waste derived from mussel farming in European Waters.
- Contribute to climate change mitigation in terms of sequestration of atmospheric carbon, this study will assess the potential of ARs to store and sequester blue carbon below mussel culture sites.

Species target & habitat: Species target: macrobenthic invertebrates, benthic macrofauna and the European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) as an endanger species; Habitat: Soft bottoms, Sandy bottoms, Maerl bottoms

Location: the outer part of the Ría de Vigo, in front of the beach of Limens

Criteria for site selection: The locality chosen for restoration actions is representative of the area, with a medium intensity of mussel farming and high fishing pressure

Adopted experimental design: The study will be conducted in two different sites: under mussel rafts and on sandy bottom without rafts. Three AR units will be deployed at each study site, resulting

in a total of two sites with ARs under mussel rafts (3 replicates for site) and two control sites without ARs, as well as two sites on sandy bottom with and without ARs.

Material: A total of twelve artificial reefs units will be installed at soft bottoms in Ría de Vigo (12-15 m depth). Each unit is composed of three cement blocks attached, covered with similar shapes to Maërl beds and holes of different sizes to accelerate the colonisation and provide shelter for fishes and invertebrates.

2.5 Madeira, Portugal

The objective of the Case Study is rocky subtidal restoration under protected and not protected conditions to test potential synergistic interaction between passive and active restoration. The idea is also to reduce urchin densities, by culling.

The experimental design is featured by two protected and two not protected locations. In each location, three replicated plots will be dedicated to grazing reduction, three to facilitate algal recover with the use of artificial structures, three in which grazing reduction and artificial structures will be combined, three control plots.

The experiment will provide relevant information on how active and passive restoration combined with controlled herbivory and adopting NBS can boost the recovery of disturbed systems this supporting theory and practice in ecological restoration.

3. Literature review

We used the same literature review carried out to support Deliverable 3.1. The literature review was conducted to identify restoration protocols adopted in different marine ecosystems worldwide with special reference to the habitats identified in the CLIMAREST demonstration sites (seagrasses, oyster reefs, algal and kelp forests). The process of inclusion in the search of both scientific (through WoS and Scopus) and grey literature, is described in the Deliverable 3.1. For the analysis we extracted the following numbers of studies across habitats:

- Seagrass: 5
- Saltmarshes: 2
- Oyster reefs: 2
- Algal and Kelp forests: 8

4. Seagrass meadows

4.1 Examples of restoration using different methods

Derrenbacker and Lewis (1982) studied three methods of seagrass planting (use of long steel staples to anchor the seagrass, hand-broadcast *Thalassia testudinum* seedlings, sections of *T. testudinum* rhizomes with attached short shoots transplanted). They were evaluated in an area of Lake Surprise, Key Largo, Florida which had been impacted by water pipeline installation. **The experimental design** includes the selection of three **areas** with different impacts: moderately impacted (shell hash) area, a severely impacted (fine silt) area, and a severely impacted (rocky) area. This comparison

requires a **note of caution** since the observed differences might be attributed both to the impact gradient and to the substrate, without the possibility to tease apart the effects of the two factors from the natural variability of the system.

A total of sixteen 2x2 m experimental plots were allocated to this restoration intervention. In each of the three areas, one unvegetated plot (2x2 m) was located. **Various combinations of seagrass species and planting methods** were tested in a total of 13 plots: the rocky area contained one experimental plot planted with *H. wrightii* alone; the moderately impacted and fine silt areas each contained one plot planted with *H. wrightii* alone, two plots planted with a combination of *H. wrightii* and *T. testudinum* seedlings, two plots planted with *T. testudinum* seedlings alone, and one plot planted with *Thalassia* rhizomes with short shoots alone. Seven plots out of sixteen were in a moderately impacted area, seven out of sixteen in a severely impacted (fine silt) area, and two were in a severely impacted rocky area.

Time: Plots were monitored monthly over a period of **7 months**.

The response variables: shoot length (cm), shoot number, shoot width (mm), percent coverage (visual estimates), density (10x10 m² quadrat), and % survival (*Thalassia*).

Main results: After 7 months *H. wrightii* had 100%, 98% and 18% coverage in the moderately, severely (fine silt) and severely (rocky) impacted experimental areas, respectively. After 7 months *T. testudinum* seedlings had 5% and 44% survival rates in the moderately and severely (fine silt) impacted experimental areas, respectively. *T. testudinum* rhizomes with short shoots had a 75% survival rate in both the moderately and severely (fine silt) impacted areas. The Authors explain the obtained success in terms of high organic sediments supporting the process.

In the study of Davis and Short (1997), Authors used the '**horizontal rhizome method**', and transplanted 2.52 ha of eelgrass in the Great Bay Estuary, New Hampshire, to create the largest eelgrass transplanting project ever attempted in the United States. **The principal aim was to mitigate port expansion impacts on an existing eelgrass population.**

The **experimental design** shows 6 transplant sites located in the intertidal zone, other 6 transplant sites located in the subtidal zone, plus **one** control site, represented by a naturally occurring eelgrass bed, one donor site (6.0 ha) and one impacted site of the proposed pier construction. In 1993, all collecting was confined to three adjacent 150 m x 300 m rectangles within the donor bed. In 1994, authors randomly selected new collecting sites outside the 1993 harvest area and used the same collection method. To protect transplanted eelgrass from horseshoe crabs (*Limulus polyphemus*) and green crabs (*Carcinus maenas*) they used temporary cages (like those reported in Fonseca et al. 1994), with forty-two percent of the grids caged.

Time: The total collection from the donor site was conducted over two years, plus a **15-year monitoring period**. Aerial photography is obtained **annually** to assess bed continuity and calculate the overall extent of the beds.

Response variables: production leaf biomass, shoot density, and 2-sided leaf area index

Main results: Shoot density at one transplant site in the intertidal exceeded that of the control site within 1 year of transplanting. Shoot density at all subtidal transplant sites surpassed that of the control site within 2 years. One-year survival rates at three subtidal transplant sites were 75-95% for 1993 transplants and 98-99% at four of the five subtidal sites planted in 1994. Instead, sea ice damage, in conjunction with tidal action, caused a lack of success in intertidal transplanting (sites had 0-15% survival). The authors affirmed that their horizontal rhizome method was a **successful**, minimum-impact technique for large-scale eelgrass transplanting efforts.

Pickerell et al. (2005) described an innovative method of dispersing *Zostera marina* L. (eelgrass) seed. They collected reproductive shoots of *Z. marina* L., transported to the laboratory and all ripening fruits were counted.

The design includes only one site, in an area deemed appropriate for restoration based on historical occurrence of *Z. marina* prior to a nuisance “brown tide” bloom in 1993 and 1994 and the success of previous broadcast seeding trials. In order to provide a precise grid facilitating monitoring during this first trial, buoy grids without nets were set out a week prior to the harvest of reproductive shoots. Each grid covered an area of 0.04 ha and consisted of three parallel rows of five buoys; spacing between buoys was 4.5 m on center (OC), providing approximately 1.5 m of overlap between adjacent buoy arcs. Buoy lines circled an area of approximately 30 m².

Fig. 3. Shows the components of a single buoy dispersal unit. (Pickerell et al., 2005)

Time: The **site was visited weekly** to observe the **progress of seed release** and determine if any of the buoys had been moved from the grid or otherwise disturbed.

Response variables: **Seedling abundance and distribution** in the plots were determined **a year later**, by counting the number of shoots in a 3 m² sampling grid subdivided into 12 subunits of 0.25 m². Counts were completed along longitudinal transects running the entire length of the plot. The area adjacent to the plots was observed for the presence of seedlings. An estimate of lateral shoot formation was determined by randomly excavating 10 groups of shoots in each of the plots, counting

the number of shoots per genet and returning the plants to the bottom. This number was used later to transform the raw seedling density numbers to seedling recruitment values.

Main results: Observations of individual nets, though not quantitative, indicated that seeds were released throughout the entire 4 weeks of deployment. Most of the seeds appear to have been released within the first 3 weeks. An estimate of seedling recruitment was calculated based on counting all the shoots within one of the buoy plots. In this plot, a total of 10,330 seedlings were observed and after correcting for the presence of laterals (i.e., 2.8 per shoot), total seed yield was estimated at 3689. Based on this number and a predicted yield of 53,400 (i.e., 3560 seeds per net multiplied by 15 nets) seedling recruitment was calculated to be 6.9%. Few seedlings were observed outside the plots; in all cases, they were found within 2 m of the plot boundaries.

The influence of the direction and frequency of wind on seedling distribution during the 5 weeks of deployment is clearly seen. The highest density of seedlings is directly opposite the strongest wind vector. Observations of buoy movements relative to tide stage and wind direction indicated that wind was an important factor in determining the position of the buoys at any point in time. The simplicity of our method, as well as the fact that a storage and handling facility is not required, allows for a larger pool of practitioners to become involved in the process of seagrass restoration than was previously possible. Their system design can also be adapted to other species of submersed aquatic vegetation with similar flowering ecologies (e.g., *Potamogeton pectinatus*, *Potamogeton pusillus* and *Potamogeton perfoliatus*). However, trial experiments are needed to determine appropriate collection methods, net mesh size and buoy spacing.

4.2 Anchoring of shoots with iron nails

The study of Lange et al. (2022) describes a large-scale eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) transplantation experiment conducted within a shallow Danish estuary, with the aim to demonstrate a marine instrument that can support Danish national plans by facilitating nutrient retention in the estuaries, assessing rates of nutrient retention and burial together with other ecosystem services.

To select the site for the large-scale transplantation experiment, authors conducted a **3-step site** selection strategy based on qualitative assessments of vegetation using aerial photos, inspection of potential sites with assessments of stressor presence and potential growth conditions, and transplantation tests for a final assessment of site suitability and methodology. The large-scale transplantation was located at the test site with the highest shoot production.

The **experimental design** for the **Small-scale transplantation trials** for site and method selection was featured by **3 sites** (A, B, and C) (Fig. 4). In each site, there were three replicates for three treatments with randomized order with a 2 m distance between replicates. In total, 9 replicates for each treatment. The 3 treatments were represented by control plots (1×1 m) with 24 eelgrass transplants; plots (1×1 m) with 24 eelgrass transplants surrounded by 2 cm mesh plastic net enclosures (3×3 m, 0.5 m high) with baited (0.5 l of crushed mussels) crab traps (a trap was placed both in and outside of the net enclosure); plots with 24 eelgrass transplants shoots within poly-

propylene cylinders secured halfway into the sediments with metal poles (1.1 m). In each plot, shoots were transplanted with 3 rows of 8 shoots with 0.14 m between shoots and 0.5 m between rows.

Fig. 4. Horsens Fjord, Denmark, showing locations (Sites A, B, and C) of the 3 transplantation tests. The large-scale eelgrass transplantation was established at Site C. (Lange et al., 2022)

The authors selected the C site, with an area of 51 × 78 m, for the **Large-scale transplantation experiment**. The **experimental design** provides 192 plots (2×2 m area which consisted of 5 rows of 15 transplanted shoots with 0.14 m between shoots and 0.5 m between rows) that were transplanted in an expanded checkerboard pattern. The 192 plots were distributed into 6 subfields (24×24) of 32 plots each, with 3 meters between the subfields. Two methods of transplant anchoring, V-stakes, and weighted shoot were each randomly assigned into 3 subfields. The initial transplanted shoot density within each plot was 14 shoots m⁻². Net enclosures and mussel-baited crab traps were used along the perimeter of the area, there were ~15 m between the transplants and the net. Crab traps were placed along the outside of the net every ~15 m.

Fig. 5. Drone mapping of the large-scale transplantation to capture changes during monitoring (2 years) (Lange et al., 2022)

Time: The large-scale transplantation lasted 5 working days.

Main results: Shoot densities developed rapidly, achieving a 70-fold increase in density after about 2 years. A rapid edge expansion (0.32 m yr^{-1}) of the transplanted area was detected using drone-based monitoring. The authors highlight the success of the experiment, important ecosystem services were already restored after 2 years from the experiment.

4.3 The importance of the context and the effectiveness of seedlings

The study of Terrados and Cédrañ (2013) documents the results of two test-transplants using *Posidonia oceanica* seedlings in an area where this Mediterranean seagrass was lost as a consequence of fish farming. The authors had two principal aims: to test if current environmental conditions in the impacted area allow the survival of *P. oceanica* seedlings and to test if seedlings planted in dead matte were able to resist uprooting.

Fig. 6. Location of the site and layout of seedlings and treatment levels in plots for Experiment 1 (substratum type, planting level) and Experiment 2 (anchoring). Black and gray squares represent Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 plots, respectively. The distance between plots in the map is not to scale (Terrados and Cédrañ 2013)

Fig. 7. *Posidonia oceanica*. Drawings of anchoring systems and planting levels used in Experiment 1, substratum type and planting level (A, B), and Experiment 2, anchoring (B, C). Mesh size of mesh-pots is 1 cm^2 (Terrados and Cédrañ 2013)

Two experiments were performed to test the effects of **substratum type** (dead matte vs. meadow) and **planting level** (above vs. below bottom surface) on **seedling survivorship** and **leaf development**.

First experiment: Three experimental areas were selected along the boundary between the impacted area (dead matte) and the *P. oceanica* meadow; the distance between consecutive areas was 25 m. Seedlings were planted following a two-way factorial design with **two fixed factors**, substratum type (dead matte vs. meadow) and planting level (above vs. below substratum surface) (Figures 6 and 7A, B). A “dead matte” plot and a “meadow” plot were established on either side of the boundary (Figure 6), with a total of 6 plots, three for each substrate. Each plot was made up of four parallel lines of six seedlings: the distance between seedlings in a line was 2 m, as was the distance between lines (Figure 6). Similar-sized seedlings were selected and were assigned haphazardly to the three areas. A total of 24 seedlings were planted in each plot, and the planting level was assigned alternately to the seedlings so that there were 12 seedlings per plot and planting level.

Time: The plots were monitored after 1, 2, and 3 years.

The second experiment was conducted within the impacted area, where six experimental plots were haphazardly selected, and 24 seedlings were randomly assigned to each plot. Seedlings were planted either firmly anchored in dead matte or without any anchoring other than their roots, that is, “mesh-pot” vs. “natural” anchoring (Figures 6). Half of the seedlings were planted inside mesh pots below the substratum surface (Figure 7), whereas the other half was carefully planted by hand, leaving the seed coat just below the surface of the substratum. Each plot was made up of four parallel lines of six seedlings, the distance between consecutive seedlings in a line was 2 m, the distance between lines was 2 m and the factor levels (“mesh-pot” vs. “natural” anchoring) were alternated along the lines (Figure 6).

Time: The monitoring activities were conducted in the surviving seedlings after 1 and 2 years.

Main results: Survivorship in dead matte was 44 % after 3 years and was not affected by planting level, instead, seedling planting inside the meadow led to complete mortality after 3 years. Seedling survivorship was not affected by the type of seedling anchoring. The authors highlighted that dead matte allows the planting of seedlings without anchoring, and this facilitates restoration work without compromising seedling survivorship, but restoration success will be achieved only in the very long term and only if the agents driving *P. oceanica* loss are eliminated. Low propagule availability is another constraint of *P. oceanica* planting.

5. Oyster reefs

5.1 Effects of cathodically protected steel vs plastic for oyster restoration mats

The study of Hunsucker et al. (2021) was designed to **determine the efficacy of mineral accretion using oyster mat structures**, with the process driven using a solar panel instead of Direct Current (DC) power sources reported in previous studies. Steel mesh oyster mats were attached to an

impressed current cathodic protection system to develop mineral accretion. The objective was to determine if mineral accretion mats were as effective at promoting the growth of oysters as plastic oyster mats. It is believed the creation of the mineral accretion structures will enhance oyster growth, which in turn provides increased filtration and improvement to local water quality. The structures will also create habitat for organisms associated with oyster reefs, such as juvenile fish, barnacles, crabs, shrimp, mussels, tunicates, snails, and algae.

Response variables were, among the others, oyster recruitment and growth.

All steel mats were subjected to pre-chalking to develop a thin mineral accretion layer, prior to deployment. This prevented the steel from rusting and would allow for ease of deployment at more remote locations. After pre-chalking, mats were rinsed and deployed at three distinct locations along the east coast of Florida. This study was carried out along the coast of Florida where **three locations** were selected at a distance of tens of kilometers.

Fig. 8. Steel and plastic mats were deployed at three locations along the east coast of Florida, within the Indian River Lagoon system: Port Canaveral, Melbourne Beach, and Grant (Hunsucker et al., 2021)

At each location, **three replicates** of both steel and plastic mats were placed and the **three replicates** on steel were connected via marine grade wires to a solar panel to continue mineral accretion.

The three locations **were not similar** each other since, for instance, Port Canaveral is located about 4 km from the Atlantic Ocean, representative of open water conditions. However, based on pilot projects and previous field work, all three sites were considered appropriate for the development of mineral accretion and oyster settlement. All oyster mats were at their final immersion site in early August 2019. However, formal comparisons considered these differences might be difficult.

For the description of the methods, please refer to Hunsucker et al. (2021).

Fig. 9. Oyster restoration mats (45.7 cm by 45.7 cm) which constructed of a mild steel (left) and aquaculture grade plastic (right) (Hunsucker et al., 2021)

Time: Materials were **monitored weekly, for three months.**

In this study, researchers had to deal with **extreme events**. After five weeks from the experimental set up, all mats were moved to a secure location in preparation for Hurricane Dorian. The hurricane sites provided immersion and protection from the storm, but had a lower salinity (<10 ppt) compared to the regular sites. All mats were returned to the test sites within about a two-week period and continued to be monitored for remainder of the three-month immersion.

Oyster recruitment was observed after one month at all three of the test locations. At this time, the number of observed oyster spat **was comparable between the plastic and steel mats**. At week five, all test sites had oyster settlement on the steel mats, whereas settlement was only observed on the plastic mats at Grant.

Main results: at the end of the experiment, there were 70 oysters recorded on the steel mats compared to 12 on the plastic mats. In addition to oyster spat growing on the dead and dried oyster substrate, they were also found growing directly on the steel mesh.

The steel mats were effective at promoting the growth of oysters, but the overall recruitment was dependent on the test site and each varied based on environmental and ecological conditions. At the Melbourne Beach location, there was **a significantly greater presence of oysters on the steel**

compared to the plastic. At Port Canaveral and Grant, **oyster growth at times was greater on the steel but at the end of the three-month period, numbers were similar between the steel and plastic.** Based on the oyster counts alone, it is apparent that the steel mats can promote and sustain oyster growth at a rate greater than or equivalent to the traditionally used plastic mats.

5.2 Substrates and tidal elevation

In the study of White et al. (2009) to restore a population of *Ostrea lurida*, drastically compromised and incapable of natural recovery, **various types of substrates and different tidal elevations** have been tested, which are identified as factors capable of influencing the restoration of this species. The aim of the project was to assess the limits of the recovery of *O. lurida* and explore techniques to improve the success of restoration efforts. The study was conducted in the North Bay Oyster Reserve (Puget Sound, Washington, United States) and the initial condition is represented by three different tide levels (+0.3m, 0m, -0.3m) in which 3 rows were distributed, one for each level, of ten experimental units represented by squares of 1 m²; within the squares, six different types of substrate were **randomly** placed: bare rock, gravel, crushed shell of *Crassostrea gigas* (Pacific oyster), whole shell of *C. gigas*, whole shell of *O. lurida* and live *O. lurida*, with 5 replicates for each substrate. The experimental design provides, therefore, 30 experimental units, positioned at a distance of about 2 meters from each other. **Two monitoring campaigns** were carried out after 5 and 11 months from experimental set up.

Response variables: *O. lurida* recruit density was calculated for the 3 tidal heights and the 6 substrates, and post-settlement mortality was evaluated.

Main results: Unfortunately, the results obtained do not guarantee the achievement of the restoration success because statistically no significant differences were found in the survival rate or in the number of recruits according to the type of substrate or the level of tide. This work represents, however, a starting point to address new successful restoration experiments that can use as a basis of their experimental designs the lowest tide level (-0.3m) and the substrate formed by shells of *Ostrea lurida*, which represent, in any case, the factors with the most promising results of this experiment.

6. Kelp forests

6.1 Effect of herbivory and thresholds of change

Leinaas et al. (1996) documented the response of the species *Laminaria saccharina* and *Laminaria hyperborea* to reduced grazing pressure of *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* through the analysis of the recovery patterns of the kelp forest in an area where historically the two species were recorded. Responses from the sea urchin population structure to increased kelp cover were also studied. During the study, an unexpected mass mortality event, which involved the area, was instrumental in providing valuable information on reducing the density of sea urchins needed to initiate kelp recovery.

The **response variables** were sea urchin density and algal cover.

The study was conducted near the island of Vega (Norway) with **two sampling sites** represented by two skerries separated by a 5 m sand tongue; one skerry is the experimental site, where all sea urchins between 0 and 10 m in depth were manually removed, and the other was the **only, unmanipulated control**. As recognized also by the Authors, the replication level was actually very limited. Thus, eleven additional sites were monitored to assess whether changes in vegetation at the manipulated site could be linked to natural fluctuations or to the sea urchin removal. A photographic sampling, with five replicated photographs taken within a frame of 0.25 m² at three different depths (2, 5, 10 m) and along transects of 30 m (on the manipulated site), 50 m (in the control site) and 10-15 m wide, was conducted to calculate algal coverage at the sampling site, at the control site and at three of the eleven sites already monitored. The density of sea urchins, on the other hand, was estimated randomly with ten squares of 0.25 m² at three depths and along the same transects; at a depth of 5 m, in addition, about 60-120 sea urchins were measured with the callipers to estimate their size, discarding those with a diameter less than 10 mm. For more information on the structure of the vegetation, algae were collected from 0.25 m to 2 m of depth, with 7 replicates per site, in the 5 sites already mentioned; the algae were counted and measured in length.

Fig. 10. The study sites in a group of small islets and skerries north of Vega Island: 1 experimental skerry, 2 control, 3, 4 and 5 other sites where sea urchin density and algal cover have been recorded since 1991 (Steinskjær, Nilsarentsskjær and Sandø respectively). Unnumbered arrows point to sites where persistence of the barren state was observed until summer 1991 (Leinaas et al., 1995)

Time: Sampling was carried out for a total of five years. After the first three years of the experimental set up a mass mortality event of the sea urchins affected the studied area. In the final analyses, this disturbance event was also included in the ANOVA, to quantify the eventual effect of this disturbance on recovery patterns and population structure.

Main results: the recovery of kelps reflects the degree of reduction in the density of sea urchins: moderate reductions in the density of sea urchins allowed only annual algae growth (*L. saccharina*)

with the potential of shifting again towards a barren state, while stronger reductions induced the recovery of the forest of *L. hyperborea*. The study suggests that about 10 individuals/m² of *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* would prevent the recovery of a forest **in the upper subtidal**, about one-third of the densities originally observed in the area. A density of 20-25 individuals per m² would maintain the area as barren. At **5-10 m of depth**, 5-10 sea urchins per m² are enough to maintain the barren because the algae have a reduced growth linked to the greater depth and are thus more vulnerable to grazing.

The article does not mention the success of the restoration since the main purpose was to identify the threshold of the number of sea urchins allowing the recovery of the system, without further human intervention.

6.2 Use of green gravel as a new restoration method

Fredriksen et al. (2020) developed and tested “green gravel”, a novel restoration technique for kelp forests, which overcomes many limitations of current approaches. Restoring reefs using green gravel requires little investment and provides potential pathways to propagate resistant genotypes that could ‘future proof’ vulnerable kelp forests to future stress. Moreover, the technique is applicable to both laminarian and fucoid kelp forests. To test the effectiveness of different transplantation techniques the gravel was out-planted using three different methods: (1) divers placed the gravel in open boxes (30×40 cm) on the seafloor at 7 m depth, (2) divers laid the gravel in open plots on bare rock at 7 m depth, and (3) gravel were dropped to 3 m and 7 m depth from a boat. Gravel was dropped from the surface by overturning a tray of gravel over the side of the boat, while a diver marked the landing site.

Fig 11. Work flow for making green gravel. Fertile plants are collected (A) and reproductive tissue isolated for zoospore release (B). Small rocks are seeded in trays by adding spore solution (C). After a few weeks small sporophytes are visible (D). Green gravel are scattered on the reef (E) where they continue to grow (F). Photo credits: H. Steen, all photos. (Fredriksen et al., 2020)

The design included **one** donor site and field sites. The donor site was outside Flødevigen Research Station (southern Norway) where fertile kelp plants (*Saccharina latissima*) with visible sori were collected in autumn (n = 10–15) and sporogenic tissue was excised for zoospore release. Kelp zoospores were added to small rocks (Fig. 11 B,C) with high, medium and low starting densities,

respectively. The **field sites** were located in a semi-protected area with patchy kelp (2–20% canopy cover) and turf-dominated reefs and mainly coarse sedimentary substrate. The response variables were kelp length, growth and green gravel retention.

To test whether gravel could be retained on rocky reefs, divers transplanted green gravel onto bare and turf-covered reefs at 6 m depth at 4 sites in early winter. At each site, a handful of gravel was placed on the seafloor inside 3 cleared 0.25 m² plots or inside 3 'open plots' with high turf-algae cover (n = 5–7 gravel in each plot). Gravel was covered with small kelp sporelings <2 cm length. Cleared plot treatments were created by removing all turf algae with a scraper from a 0.25 m² quadrat, leaving only bare rock and encrusting coralline algae. Substrate (turf and bare rock) was treated as a fixed factor and study sites and replicated plots were treated as random factors with plots nested within sites.

Fig. 12. Healthy sugar kelp forests (*Saccharina latissima*, A) disappeared along the southern coast of Norway in 2002. Large tracts of coast once dominated by sugar kelp now only have scattered individuals, and the seafloor is instead covered by a dense carpet of turf algae (B). This loss has been persistent, warranting investigation of restoration techniques - such as green gravel (C) - to aid recovery. Photo credits: K. Filbee-Dexter (A), T. Wernberg (B), S. Fredriksen (C). (Fredriksen et al., 2020)

Main Results: The out-planted kelp had high survival and growth over 9 months, even when dropped from the surface. Seeded juvenile kelps can eventually overgrow the green gravel and attach to the surrounding substrate or underlying rock, which suggests the plants could be retained on these reefs. Cost assessment is also available in the study.

6.3 Artificial structures

The objectives of study of Oyamada et al. (2008) were to observe the algal succession, the growth of *Ecklonia cava* and other attached organisms on two types of artificial-reef blocks. **The experiment design** included in **one** site, five Marine Blocks (1m³) and five concrete blocks (1m³) installed close to *E. cava* beds, compared to natural seaweed beds, placed at a depth of 7 m around the coastal frontage of Jogashima, Kanagawa, Japan. They replaced five concrete blocks with five cubic Marine Blocks with a size of 1m³. The Authors stress that a concrete block is an

appropriate reference substrate for evaluating artificial substrates for seaweed bed development, because there are already many case studies on concrete blocks in the literature.

Fig.13. Marine block (1m × 1m × 1m). (Oyamada et al., 2008)

The area consists mainly of rocky ledges, and there is a natural marine forest of *Ecklonia cava*, a large perennial brown alga, whose lifetime is 3–4 years.

The blocks were placed in November 2001 on relatively flat areas of seafloor scattered across this terrain. Scuba-diving observations and measurements, to count the number of *E. cava* and *Sargassum* plants and other attached organisms attached to each block, were continued until April 2006.

Response variables: the number and length of all *E. cava* individuals on the upper surface (1×1m) of each of the five blocks and identified the major seaweeds and attached organisms. The observation frequency was set to be once every 2–5 months.

Fig.14. a,b Photos of top surfaces in October 2002. a Marine Block. The surface is covered with *Ecklonia cava*. b Concrete Block. *Ecklonia cava* is attached to the edge of the block (Oyamada et al., 2008).

Main results: the succession in the algal vegetation on blocks was similar to that in the vegetation in the surrounding natural marine forests of *E. cava*. In the succession, diatoms first covered blocks, and then small annual algae appeared, and ultimately *E. cava*, a large perennial alga, became dominant and formed stable vegetation on nearby natural rock reefs. Such processes are normally seen in natural seaweed vegetation and so it can be concluded that both Marine Blocks and concrete blocks can form artificial reefs having the same functions as natural rocky reefs. Further study showed that the number and weight of *E. cava* on natural reefs was smaller than that on blocks, but *E. cava* on natural reefs was longer.

7. Algal forests

Different experimental designs used to restore macroalgal forests have been adopted using *in situ* and *ex situ* restoration strategies and considering different approaches to affect the .

7.1 Effect of conspecific adults and grazers

A large-scale restoration intervention is illustrated in the study by Tamburello et al. (2019), in which an *ex situ* active restoration approach was used to test the effect of conspecific adult individuals, macrograzers and mesograzers on *Cystoseira amentacea* germlings.

The initial conditions are represented by two different *Cystoseira amentacea* forests: one donor, characterized by >80% coverage, and the other to be restored, characterized by <10% coverage. For each condition, two locations were randomly identified, at a distance of about ten km from each other. For each location, then, two sites were chosen, distant from each other in the order of hundreds of meters, in which 18 experimental units were fixed (20x20 squares). Five tiles with laboratory-grown *Cystoseira amentacea* germlings, obtained from fertile fronds of donor populations, were placed in every experimental unit. In order to assess the effect of conspecific adult individuals on germlings, in half of the experimental units (9) of the sites to be restored adult individuals were transplanted, previously taken from half of the experimental units of the donor sites. To assess the influence of the macrograzers, cages were fixed in twelve experimental units for each site, half of which had openings of 4 cm on their side to allow access to mesograzers.

Figure 15. Experimental design from Tamburello et al. (2019)

Six experimental units, instead, had no cages. For each condition, there were therefore three replicates. The work highlights the need to have **nursery facilities** in proximity to restoration sites to contribute significantly to the success of the intervention. One potential pitfall of the study was represented by a limited number of sites and the total duration of the study was limited to three months, too short a time to fully assess the success of the restoration actions. Survival of *Cystoseira* germlins in the field was not affected by the presence of conspecific adults, while the limitation of grazers appears to be crucial to the success of the experiment.

7.2 Combining active and passive restoration

In the work of Medrano et al. (2020), the success of active revegetation techniques as a tool to promote forests of *Treptacantha elegans* reduced to barren of sea urchin was tested, to assess the potential success of active restoration techniques (*in situ*) combined with passive restoration and marine protection.

The design for active revegetation initially includes 10 locations: six degraded barren grounds to revegetate (3 inside the NTZ and 3 outside), two dense *T. elegans* forests as reference sites of forest state (1 inside the NTZ and 1 outside), and two degraded barren grounds as reference sites of degraded habitat (1 inside the NTZ and 1 outside). Given the small size of the NTZ, they selected a limited number of reference areas. All 10 locations were selected in the 5–10 m depth range (5 inside the NTZ and 5 outside) covering the most diverse range of barren grounds' sizes and local-scale variability given the limited size of the NTZ area (93 ha).

In the six areas of barren to be restored, in addition to having carried out active restoration with the *in situ* technique, sea urchins were removed completely to eliminate the impact of herbivory.

Once the successful technique was estimated in preliminary tests, in spring 2018, the *in situ* seedling technique was implemented within the 6 degraded barren grounds (3 inside the NTZ and 3 outside) and the 4 reference sites. Taking advantage of this experimental setup, they additionally tested three types of settlement collectors: stone plates (flat manufactured limestone), plots of original substrate (unmanipulated limestone substrate, mainly covered by the representative algal assemblages), and plots of scraped and cleared substrate of approximately 25 cm² area each. Six collectors of each type were randomly placed or delimited around the six seeding bags in each experimental site. Revegetation success was assessed 1 year later in the six barren grounds, but was only achieved after combining active with passive restoration strategies (see also Fig. 16 for details).

Results encourage revegetation of barren grounds to shift from less productive habitats to complex *T. elegans* forests, highlight the potential of the combined passive and active restoration strategies, as well as the important role of marine reserves not only in conservation but also in ecological restoration. The outcomes of the papers are that active revegetation practices alone are insufficient to restore marine degraded grounds and effective when combined with passive restoration practices. Revegetation of degraded barren grounds in marine protected areas triggers the recovery of marine

forests. More and well-enforced No-Take marine reserves are essential for management purposes and ecological restoration.

Figure 16. Diagram showing the experimental design and the three-step *T. elegans* revegetation protocol (Medrano et al., 2020)

7.3 *In situ* vs *ex situ* restoration

The study carried out by Verdura et al. (2019), focuses on the restoration of algal forests of *Cystoseira barbata* in sites where this species disappeared in the 80s specifically on the island of Menorca (Balearic Islands, NW Mediterranean) which has been a UNESCO biosphere reserve since 1993.

The study includes two different techniques of non-destructive restoration *in situ* and *ex situ*.

The experimental design of the *in situ* technique includes: a donor site, located in Fornells Bay where fertile apical branches of wild specimens have been collected, two sites affected by the restoration action, at Cala Teulera, where the species *C. barbata* was present until the 1970s and then was found extinct. Three control sites also located in the Fornells Bay where 20 squares (20 x 20) randomly placed, were calculated the densities and the distribution of the dimensional structure of

three different populations of *C. barbata*, at the beginning and end of the experiment (2011, 2016, 2017).

The technique involved the use of eight dispersal bags per site containing the fertile apical branches, placed on a metal support 25 cm from the bottom. Randomly and at a distance ranging from 0.1 to 4m from the dispersal bags, flat stones (20 x 20) cleaned by all organisms to facilitate the rooting of the zygotes of *C. barbata*. The dispersal bags were removed after four days.

The monitoring of the implants was carried out every month and from the fifth month the densities and the distribution of the dimensional structure of the young individuals of *C. barbata* were detected. At the same time, the dispersion capacity of the zygotes of *C. barbata* was evaluated by placing two additional bags for each site. The stones (about 20 x 20) were placed as follows: six stones just below the dispersion bags (0 m), six at a distance of 2 m, and finally six at a distance of 4 m. Again, the dispersal bags were removed after 4 days, and the number of recruits from each stone was counted in August 2011.

Fig. 16. Location of the reference populations (A) and the restored area (B). (Verdura et al., 2019)

Fig. 17. Dispersion range capacity under in situ recruitment (Verdura et al., 2019)

The experimental design of the *ex situ* technique includes the following steps: from the same donor site described for the technique *in situ* the fertile apical branches were placed in aquaria of 12 liters

on the bottom of which were placed 16 flat rocks (about 20x20) to root the zygotes of *C. barbata*. After three months of growth in the aquarium, the colonized rocks were transported to the two sites subject to restoration and were placed about 25 m from the plants obtained with the technique *in situ*. Growth monitoring was conducted twice in the first year, and once in the following years.

The results obtained were similar between the two applied restoration techniques. After an initial mortality comparable to that which normally occurs in nature, the density of individuals in the plants has settled and there are no significant differences with the control sites. These values remained the same (despite some fluctuations) until the end of the experiment. The coverage of *C. barbata* at the end of the experiment is 25 m².

7.4 *Ex situ* restoration technique with facilities far from restoration sites

De La Fuente et al. (2019), conducted the restoration of *Cystoseira amentacea* var. *scripta* using an *ex situ* restoration technique. Apical fronds (ca. three cm in length) holding mature receptacles were collected in June from a healthy population located in the Portofino MPA (donor site) along a 200-m stretch of coastline. After a laboratory culturing period, the juveniles were transplanted into the Cinque Terre MPA (receiving site; approximately 80 km from the donor site)

The fertile apices were transported to Trieste where they were stored in aquaria for fertilization. Inside the tanks under the fertile apexes were placed 450 clay disks (diameter 4.5 cm) with a hole (0.6 cm) in the center for subsequent placement in the sea. After about a month of growth in the inplant, the diskettes were transferred to the donor site. During outplanting, the tiles were carefully transported to the field. Eight patches were established in the previous weeks: 50 holes were drilled in each patch and screws placed within them in advance. On the day of implementation, the tiles were quickly screwed to the rocks. Overall, the deployment of 400 tiles was performed in approximately 5 h.

The monitoring started from the time of the plant (T0) and continued for about two months (T0-T4). In each monitoring, 20 random photos were taken on the 50 patches diskettes and analyzed in the laboratory with *Imagej* software, to estimate the percentage of coating and survival of small individuals of *C. amentacea*.

The results show from the moment of the implantation of the tiles in the donor site a reduction of about 60% of the percentage coating.

At the same time, the heights of the juveniles between T0 and T4 were measured from less than 6 mm of T0 to 11 mm at T4. Only in 16 tiles that remained intact after the swell was it possible to measure the height of the juveniles that was between three and six centimeters.

Fig. 18. Development of the outplanted juveniles on tiles over time (Time 0–Time 5) at the receiving site (De La Fuente et al., 2019)

Fig. 19. Map showing the location of the culture laboratory facilities and the donor (DS) and receiving (RS) sites. (De la Fuente et al., 2019)

7.5 Testing the effects of culling on reversing barrens

Guarnieri et al. (2020) during their experiment have evaluated how the subtidal rocky reef degraded to barren state can recover through the removal of sea urchins by culling since sea urchins, through their grazing, do not allow recolonization by macroalgae.

The Authors tested this approach within a Marine Protected Area where a combination of oligotrophic conditions, general depletion of fish stocks, dramatically high sea urchin densities, and the large increase of barren grounds caused by *Lithophaga lithophaga* illegal fishery have hampered the natural recovery of shallow rocky reefs.

Fig. 20. (A) Study area and (B) timeline of the restoration intervention (Guarnieri et al., 2020)

The culling of sea urchins took place within the no-take/no-access zone called "La Stream" (Fig. 1A) which represents the area with the worst conditions in terms of desertification, with over 60% of barren. **Removal was carried out in two sites** at 5-7 m deep with an extension of 6000 m² each, low morphological complexity of the substrate (i.e., absence of ridges and depressions) and inclination (<20%). In each site, **33 culling transects** were carried out arranged perpendicularly to the coast for a length of the transect of 30 m. At the end of the experiment the divers removed about 92500 sea urchins from the two sites.

The experimental design adopted to follow pattern of recovery consisted of four factors: Time (Ti, 5 levels, fixed), Treatment (Tr, 2 levels, G– and G+, fixed and orthogonal), Site (Si, 2 levels, random, and nested in Tr), and Transect (Ts, 3 levels, random, and nested in Si) with n = 10 replicates. Sea urchin density was assessed by mean of a three-factor experimental design: Time (Ti, 5 levels, fixed), Treatment (Tr, 2 levels, fixed and orthogonal), and Site (Si, 2 levels, random, and nested in Tr) with n = 3 replicates.

Main results: Throughout the duration of the experiment, very low recolonization of sea urchins was observed, with a decreased average density of sea urchins so that further extensive removal of sea urchins was not required within the time span covered by the study. 36 months after the removal of the sea urchin, significant changes occurred in the structure of the benthic assemblages as a result of the systematic removal activity carried out at the chosen sites. A progressive reduction of the barren extension was observed, with a 50% reduction in bare substrate at the end of the monitoring

in favor of macroalgal stands. At the end of the experiment, two large areas of 6000 m² showed an overall increase in both erect and turf algae.

8. Saltmarshes

8.1 Restoration, sediment types and associated environmental variables

Chen et al. (2017), describe a **successful** restoration experiment of native *Scirpus* marshes in the Yangtze Estuary (China). They investigated the accumulation of soil organic carbon (SOC) and nitrogen (SN) in the soil profile of recently restored (2 years) and mature (natural vegetation) native *S. mariqueter* marshes.

The **experimental design** for the restoration of the Yangtze Estuary salt marshes, which disappeared over one-third during the past three decades, shows **two sample areas** selected on the base of sediment type: a muddy habitat and a silty habitat. Through the burying of transplanted soil cores with a diameter of 7.5 cm and a depth of ~15 cm containing corms of *S. mariqueter*, **three treatments** were conducted with different levels of planting densities applied in both areas, the mud-dominated area (M-YL low with 1 soil core per 1 m², M-YM medium with 2 soil cores per 1 m² and M-YH high with 4 soil cores per 1 m²), and the silt-dominated area (for which, in the end, only the S-YH high-density approach succeeded). In these transplanted soil cores, on average, there were **15 corms**. **Two controls** were present, represented by original untreated mature *S. mariqueter* marsh, of, at least, 10 years old. In addition, M-Bare and S-Bare were included as non-vegetated areas (See figure 21).

Response variables: Plant growth, shoot density and biomass, and sedimentary dynamics.

Fig 21. Location of the study area in the Chongming Dongtan salt marsh of the Yangtze Estuary and the two sampling sites (muddy site in the eastern marsh and silty site in the southern marsh). (Chen et al., 2017)

Time: In **twelve months**, the sedimentation dynamics in both the mud-dominated and silt-dominated sites were measured at monthly intervals. The aerial parts of plants were harvested, and soil samples were collected two times, **2 years** after revegetation.

Main results: In recently restored marsh characterized by muddy sediments with moderate sediment accretion, vegetation growth, and SOC and SN storage increased along with the increase in planting densities and the SOC storage was 1.14-1.52 times greater than that in non-vegetated plots after two years of revegetation. The restoration of native *S. maritima* for SOC and SN stocks is most effective when conducted in muddy sediments with good sedimentation rates and using a high planting density. In contrast, costs will be higher and recovery time longer in silty (or sandy) sediments, due to their poorer conditions for plant growth and significantly lower rates of carbon and nitrogen accumulation. This study, even though pseudoreplicated, could be considered an example of the **quick success** of restoration and has demonstrated that the revegetation and the below-ground root growth played a key role in determining SOC and SN accumulation and storage in the salt marsh.

Taylor et al. (2019) tested the effects of sediment dynamics on natural and restored *Bolboschoenus maritimus* saltmarsh. Sediment settlement, deposition, and accretion rates of natural and restored vegetation (*Bolboschoenus maritimus*) and adjacent bare mudflats in a small estuary system were studied across consecutive seasons from summer 2015 to spring 2016 to examine the success of transplantation.

Fig.22. The north shore of the Eden Estuary, Scotland. The green polygon delineates the full extent of the “Natural” saltmarsh, an area of 450 m², made up of a robust bed of *B. maritimus*. The blue polygon delineates the extent of the “Restored” area, a total of 100 m², consisting of a planted mono-specific stand of *B. maritimus*. The “Mudflat” area consisted of the entire adjacent fringing edge running along the coast between the extreme ends of the natural and restored vegetated areas. The yellow points are the location of permanent sampling points. (Taylor et al., 2019)

Experimental design: The Eden Estuary is a small mesotidal pocket estuary on the east coast of Scotland, located between the larger Firth of Forth to the south and the Tay estuary to the north, and is situated within the Firth of Tay and Eden Estuary SAC and SPA, it is also designated as a SSSI, Ramsar site and Local Nature Reserve.

Correctly, four permanent sampling points were established in three area types (natural marsh, restored marsh, and natural mudflat; $n=12$, referred to hence as “natural,” “restored,” and “mudflat”)

to study the sediment dynamics therein. The “restored” area consisted of a mono-specific stand of well-established *B. maritimus*. The “mudflat” area was an unvegetated area running adjacent to the coast between the two extreme extents of the vegetated areas.

Monitoring: Sediment deposition and settlement were sampled on 16 occasions over a year period, on each occasion sampling took place at 12 permanent points. Sampling was carried out four times in each season, this allowing a correct quantification of the temporal variability within each season. The four sampling occasions in each season spanned across a spring to neap tidal change, beginning on a spring tide. On each occasion, sediment deposition and settlement traps were deployed during low tide and remained exposed for two flood tide events, after which they were retrieved. The next sampling occasion took place the following day at low tide, this was repeated four times each season. Sediment elevation measurements were taken once per season, following the sediment deposition and settlement sampling.

Sampling aimed to capture information on the sediment regime within the study area.

Main results: It is not yet clear how the current sedimentary interactions will affect the long-term survival and evolution of this site, specifically the persistence of the restored area. Although the data suggests the site of restoration is experiencing a different biogeomorphic situation compared to the bare mudflat, which is assumed to reflect its previous state, this situation does not yet mirror its natural counterpart.

This study illustrates the subtleties of saltmarsh development and feedbacks, highlighting the **importance of site selection** in restoration activities. The “established” appearance of the restored planted saltmarsh disguises its possible vulnerability in dynamic sedimentary interactions leading to net erosion across the site.

This study highlighted the possible vulnerability of restored areas, which may visually appear established, but whose processes do not indicate a robust ecosystem; specifically, net elevation loss during the study. The **delay for restoration to achieve comparable ecological functionality to natural areas** is important to consider when carrying out restoration projects and may require additional effort once established to ensure their persistence. Such information could advance approaches and maximize the delivery of conservation objectives which are crucial to prevent the loss of these systems.

9. Final considerations

Ecosystem restoration involves innovation and experimentation, and restoration activities often result in surprises and setbacks. Because of this, it is often necessary to conduct initial experimentation to support decision-making (e.g. choice of species and spacing) or to install and test alternative treatments during the project to enable adaptive management (FAO et al., 2023).

However, our description has the aim to stress the importance of adopting rigorous experimental design in restoration and the caution needed in analysing and extrapolating results from simplistic approaches. Evaluating the effects of anthropogenic activities on organisms and environments is

fundamentally important to ensure adequate management and conservation of natural environments. Logical and methodological criteria underlying evaluation procedures are critical for detecting environmental impacts, or the effectiveness of mitigation efforts (Benedetti-Cecchi, 2004). A key step in this procedure involves the identification of an appropriate sampling designs, capable of measuring a specific effect and to tease it apart from background natural variation. The same logic has to be applied also to restoration which is a human intervention into ecological systems. Restoration should be perceived as an experimental treatment thus following the same criteria of any ecological experiment. Restoration, for its natura, is based on manipulative experiments. This is very relevant also for inferring mechanisms, but the only limit is that often manipulative studies are limited to relatively small spatial scales, few locations, and short durations, limiting the potential for generalities. Coordinated experiments can overcome this limit.

In the analyses of the literature, several issues emerge: very often just one control is included in the restoration intervention, and, also, many experiments are pseudoreplicated. This means that an inappropriate source of variability is used as reference to examine the effect of a factor. As an example, analysing effectiveness of restoration along an environmental gradient in which selected sites are also featured by different substrates translates into the consequences that potential differences at the end of the experiment in restoration effectiveness might be linked to the gradient but also to the different substrates, without the possibility to tease apart the effect of one factor from the effect of the other.

Our analyses show that despite there is an increasing number of studies improving the spatial and temporal scales of the interventions, still inconsistent methodologies and other idiosyncrasies among studies limit the direct comparisons needed to improve general knowledge.

Most studies concur that current and historical presence, site local condition assessment and choice of the actions to be carried out are central in all restoration interventions. In addition:

- 1- Species selection and donor populations are critical elements in restoration whose selection has to be addressed through a solid scientific knowledge.
- 2- Complex experiments dealing with multiple factors assessing the effects, for instance, of substrate, biotic interactions, environmental variables are important to advance restoration. However, it is necessary to specify the relationships among factors (crossed vs nested) and the nature of each factor (fixed or random). This issue is most of times not addressed in the studies (but see for exceptions Guarnieri et al., 2020; Medrano et al., 2020).
- 3- Compare replicated restoration sites to multiple controls, before and after restoration interventions, on both control and restored sites. The need of multiple controls has been largely stressed and should be always clear that reference areas must have the undisturbed assemblages and similar environmental features as disturbed areas that we want to restore.

- 4- Repeating measurements in time, to estimate temporal variability of response variables is also very important and long term experiments should be a priority.

In conclusion, considering the effort and the costs invested in restoration, rigorous experiments are a priority. In this framework, it is important starting any restoration intervention to develop partnerships among scientists, practitioners, and the local community, to ensure that the project receives an appropriate level of scientific and practical advice and assistance to optimize its success and relevance.

10. References

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